

THE IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE IN EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6595845>

Saidova Nilufar

MA Department, UzSWLU

Shukurova Z.I

Senior teacher

Annotation: *This article discusses the role of Language in Education and presents the effects of languages in educational development.*

Keywords: *Education, Education Language, development of human knowledge.*

Language is an important part of human connection. Language allows us to share our ideas, thoughts and feelings with others. By learning a language, it means you have mastered a complex system of words, structure, and grammar to effectively communicate with others.

Language is a significant factor in the learning and teaching of subjects. Over the years, the effect of the medium of instruction used in teaching has been an issue of great interest. The language through which subjects are being taught is an area of increased concern especially for Mathematics educators. Language is of key importance in all human endeavors. However, not all languages are especially developed for such use. Certain languages are well developed and more conveniently used in a particular field than other languages such that no equivalent terminology may be found in another language.

The central importance of language in education and the child's command over it is widely accepted. It's not difficult to see the reasons for this wide agreement. It's obvious that language is essential for communication, for the child as well as for everyone else. So is it essential for gaining understanding of all disciplines be it mathematics, sciences or any other. Indeed the child links to all aspects of education only through language. In fact, the child thinks, makes decisions and acts through and with language. Language is central to the child's (as everyone else's) existence as a part of society.

The above perspective is clearly necessary - in fact mandatory - if one has to appreciate the centrality of language to the child's education and growth. However, this is still a limited perspective. The limitation of this perspective is in viewing language as a "tool;" a "tool" to understand Mathematics or a "tool" to take decisions. Language may indeed be a tool, but it is also a lot more. This "lot

more” is perhaps even more determinant of the centrality of language to the child, in education and in human life in general.

Without giving “names” to the concepts, none of this is possible. These “names” are what we know as “words” in language. The development and construction of the “conceptual system” is what we call the development and gaining of understanding. So, language and understanding are dependent on each other. The existence of one is not possible without the other.

Thus, language is not merely a “tool.” It is an integral and inalienable part of understanding. It is capacitative of the human mind and selfconsciousness, as, what is the human mind but the totality of understanding! It develops with the development of understanding, and is constrained when understanding is constrained. This conclusion is of critical importance to primary education.

It's obvious that language is essential for communication, for the child as well as for everyone else. So is it essential for gaining understanding of all disciplines be it mathematics, sciences or any other. Indeed the child links to all aspects of education only through language. In fact, the child thinks, makes decisions and acts through and with language. Language is central to the child's (as everyone else's) existence as a part of society.

Moreover, language is the method of combining words to create meaning; it is the discourse between people and communities. Language exists so that one can communicate with another. Just as David Crystal states in his talk on Englishes, “You want to have a language that reflects your local interests, history and things that happen around you. All the things that happen in your language.” (2013) How one communicates with an individual will depend on the circumstance, for example a conversation between colleagues versus a stranger on the street will differ in terms of topic of discussion, body language and tone of voice. How an educator communicates with a student will shape the relationship between the two, as language determines authority or equality. The language and social experiences between a child and their peers or adult figures in their life will also determine how they communicate to another individual. Language and communication skills are imperative for a child’s education as it is the platform for other forms of development. There are many ways language can be taught; it is essential that educators understand these processes, as there are different ways of teaching language. (Grellier, 2014) The first way to look at language is as an object where language illustrates the meaning of subjects with a material form. In relation to the classroom, language in object form is structured and allows children’s language development to be studied further.

Conclusion

Summarizing, we can say that, Language plays central role in education. Learning in classrooms is primarily accomplished through language. So Language is an important factor in the learning and teaching processes

USED LITERATURE:

1. Adole, I. A. (1988). Basic Instructional Technology: A Hand Book
2. Unpublished.
3. Berko, R. M. Wolvin, A. D. Wolvin, DR, (1998) Communication:
4. A Social and Career Focus: Houghton Mifflin Co, 4th Edition.
5. Harding, D. C. (2002). Framework for Teacher Reform. The World
6. Bank Institute of Strategic Choices for Education Reform,
7. Washington D.C.
8. Nwajiobi, G. U. (1988). Communication in the Classroom, Jos
9. Challenge Press.
10. Oni, J. (1995). Educational Resources An Introduction. Abeokuta
11. G-bemiSadipo Press.
12. Sakan, B. O. (2002). "Communication in the Classroom" A Paper
13. Delivered at the Mobilization Workshop on Teachers Professional
14. Support.